

A New Synthesis of (+) Biflora-4,10(19),15-triene

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Ketalisation of ethyl-2-carbethoxy-2-(propan-1'-al-3'-yl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (II) prepared by Michael condensation of acrolein with II affords the dioxolane derivative (IV) which on decarboxylation followed by reduction furnishes the ketal-alcohol (VI). This, on oxidation and subsequent Wittig reaction using methallylidenetriphenylphosphorane, gives 5-(1',1'-ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-2,6,10-trimethyl-1,3,10-undecatriene (VIII). Deketalisation furnishes the aldehyde (IX) which is converted into the title compound through a known method.

BIFLORA-4,10(19),15-triene, a bicyclic diterpene was recently isolated by Wiemer *et al* as one of the main constituents of the oily defensive secretions released from the soldiers of East African termite *Cubitermes umbratus* Williams¹. Structure I was assigned to it on the basis of spectral studies exclusively². Further support for the formulation I was provided by its synthesis in our laboratory³. In the present communication, we wish to report a new synthesis of the biflora diterpene by a different route.

Ethyl-2-carbethoxy-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (II) was prepared by the known procedure⁴. This on treatment with acrolein afforded the aldehyde (III, 40%) which was ketalized to give the corresponding dioxolane derivative (IV) in almost quantitative yield. Compound IV was smoothly decarboxylated with sodium chloride in DMSO⁵ to furnish the ketal-ester (V, 60%) which on LAH reduction gave 2-(1',1'-ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enol (VI, 80%) as a viscous colourless oil. Oxidation of VI effected with pyridinium chlorochromate⁶ in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate produced the ketal-aldehyde (VII, 68%). Wittig reaction on VII using methallylidenetriphenylphosphorane⁷ provided 5-(1',1'-ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-2,6,10-trimethyl-1,3,10-undecatriene (VIII, 50%). Careful deketalisation of VIII in acetone-water (4 : 1) containing PTS at room temperature generated the aldehyde (IX, 70%) and it was converted into I through a known sequence⁸ which involves Lewis acid catalysed intramolecular Diels Alder reaction⁸.

Experimental

The boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded as thin films on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel G (N.C.L., Poona) containing plaster of paris (13%) was used for tlc. Neutral alumina was used for column chromatography. The organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

Ethyl-2-carbethoxy-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (II): This was prepared as reported in literature⁴. PMR (CCl_4): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-$], 1.1-1.45 (8H, *m*, H-4 and $-\text{COOCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 1.62, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s, s*, = $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 1.8-2.35 (3H, *m*, H-3 and H-5), 3.15 (1H, *d*, $J=7.5$ Hz, H-2), 4.2 (4H, *q*, $J=6$ Hz, $-\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 5.1 (1H, *br t*, $J=6$ Hz, H-6).

Ethyl-2-carbethoxy-2-(propan-1'-al-3'-yl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (III): A few drops of sodium ethoxide (10%) were added to a stirring solution of the diester (II) (27 g) in *t*-butanol (50 ml); thereafter the freshly distilled acrolein (6 g) was added

dropwise at 15-20°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2-3 hr and left at room temp. for 48 hr. The contents were decomposed with acetic acid (1-2 ml) and the *t*-butanol removed under reduced pressure. Water was added to the residue which was extracted with ether, dried, the solvent removed and residue distilled under reduced pressure to get II (13.04 g, 40%), b.p. 170-2°/5-6 mm; ir: 2710, 1720, 1640, 1450, 860; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.15-1.45 (10H, *m*, *H*-3', *H*-4 and -COOCH₂-CH₃), 1.62, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.8-2.35 (3H, *m*, *H*-3 and *H*-5), 2.45 (2H, distorted *q*, *H*-2'), 4.2 (4H, *q*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -COOCH₂-CH₃), 5.1 (1H, *br t*, *J*=6 Hz, *H*-6), 9.75 (1H, *s*, -CHO). (Found: C, 66.11; H, 9.16. C₁₈H₃₀O₅ requires C, 66.23; H, 9.26%).

Ethyl-2-carbethoxy-2-(1,1-ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (IV): A mixture of III (32.7 g), ethylene glycol (6.8 g) and PTS (100 mg) in benzene (500 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr under Dean and Stark water separator. The reaction mixture was cooled, washed with aq. sodium bicarbonate (10%), dried and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled to provide IV (27.75 g, 75%); b.p. 187-8°/5-6 mm; ir: 1725, 1650, 1440, 1050, 890, 810; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.05-1.5 (12H, *m*, *H*-2', *H*-3', *H*-4 and -COOCH₂CH₃), 1.65, 1.75 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.8-2.35 (3H, *m*, *H*-3 and *H*-5), 3.9 (4H, *br s*, -OCH₂-CH₂O-), 4.2 (4H, *q*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -COOCH₂CH₃), 4.8 [1H, *t*, *J*=5 Hz, -HC(OCH₂)₂], 5.15 (1H, *br t*, *J*=6 Hz, *H*-6). (Found: C, 64.78; H, 9.36. C₂₀H₃₄O₆ requires C, 64.84; H, 9.25%).

Ethyl-2-(1,1'-ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enoate (V): The diester (IV) (39 g) was heated at 180-5° with NaCl (9.8 g), water (9 ml) and DMSO (100 ml) for 8 hr. The DMSO was removed *in vacuo*, water added to the residue and extracted thoroughly with ether and dried. Solvent removal followed by distillation under reduced pressure yielded V (18.96 g, 60%); b.p. 165-8°/5-6 mm; ir: 1725, 1650, 1450, 1250, 1050, 860; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.1-1.5 (9H, *m*, *H*-2', *H*-3', *H*-4 and -COOCH₂CH₃), 1.6, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.8-2.4 (4H, *m*, *H*-2, *H*-3 and *H*-5), 3.9 (4H, *br s*, -OCH₂-CH₂O-), 4.2 (2H, *q*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -COOCH₂CH₃), 4.7 [1H, *t*, *J*=5 Hz, -CH(OCH₂)₂], 5.1 (1H, *br t*, *J*=6 Hz, *H*-6). (Found: C, 68.36; H, 10.08. C₁₇H₃₀O₄ requires C, 68.42; H, 10.13%).

2-(1,1'-Ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enol (VI): To a stirred suspension of LAH (1.7 g) in dry ether (150 ml) was added dropwise the ester (V) (14.9 g) in dry ether (25 ml). The mixture was left overnight at room temp. and then refluxed for 1 hr. Usual work-up with saturated solution of sodium potassium tartrate followed by solvent removal and chromatography furnished VI (10.24 g, 80%); b.p. 158-9°/5-6 mm; ir: 3390, 1650, 1450, 1040, 950, 870; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.1-1.55 (6H, *m*, *H*-4, *H*-2'

and *H*-3'), 1.6, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.8-2.3 (4H, *m*, *H*-2, *H*-3 and *H*-5), 3.35-3.7 (3H, complex pattern, -CH₂OH), 3.9 (4H, *br s*, -OCH₂-CH₂O-), 4.95 [1H, *t*, *J*=5 Hz, -CH(OCH₂)₂], 5.1 (1H, *br t*, *J*=6 Hz, *H*-6). (Found: C, 70.17; H, 10.98. C₁₅H₂₈O₈ requires C, 70.27; H, 11.01%).

2-(1,1'-Ethylene dioxy-3'-propyl)-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enal (VII): To a stirred suspension of pyridinium chlorochromate (18.0 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (200 mg) in dry dichloromethane (150 ml) at 10° was added the alcohol (VI) (12.8 g) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (20 ml) and stirring continued at room temp. for 2.5 hr, when dry ether (200 ml) was added to it and the supernatant layer decanted from the black gummy residue. The insoluble residue was thoroughly washed with ether. The combined organic solution was passed through a short column of alumina, solvent removed and the product distilled under reduced pressure to give VII (8.68 g, 68%); b.p. 120-2°/5-6 mm; ir: 2710, 1710, 1650, 1450, 1050, 880; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.1-1.5 (6H, *m*, *H*-4, *H*-2' and *H*-3'), 1.6, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.9-2.3 (3H, *m*, *H*-3 and *H*-5), 3.9 (4H, *br s*, -OCH₂-CH₂O-), 4.8 [1H, *t*, *J*=6 Hz, -CH(OCH₂)₂], 5.1 (1H, *br t*, *J*=6 Hz, *H*-6), 9.75 (1H, *s*, *H*-1). (Found: C, 70.72; H, 10.18. C₁₆H₂₆O₃ requires C, 70.83; H, 10.30%).

1,1-Ethylene dioxy-4-(2'-methyl-butadienyl)-5,9-dimethyl-8-decene (VIII): Methallylidetriphenylphosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (50%, 1.12 g) in DMSO (12 ml) and methallyltriphenylphosphonium chloride (8.1 g) in DMSO (23 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere as usual. The aldehyde (VII) (4 g) in THF (4 ml) was added dropwise to the stirred solution of phosphorane via a syringe at low temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hr and then left overnight at room temp. The contents were warmed for 6 hr at 60° while stirring continuously. The reaction mixture cooled and poured over crushed ice, extracted with ether and dried. After solvent removal, the product was chromatographed over neutral alumina to furnish VIII (2.29 g, 50%); ir: 2990, 1645, 1620, 1430, 1350, 1050, 970, 885; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-], 1.1-1.55 (6H, *m*, *H*-2, *H*-3 and *H*-6), 1.6, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.87 [3H, *s*, -CH=CH-C(CH₃)=CH₂], 1.9-2.4 (4H, *m*, *H*-4, *H*-5 and *H*-7), 3.9 (4H, *br s*, -OCH₂-CH₂O-), 4.75 (1H, *t*, *J*=4.5 Hz, *H*-1), 4.85 (2H, *s*, *H*-1'), 5.1 (1H, *br*, *H*-8), 5.87 (1H, *dd*, *J*=7 and 14 Hz, *H*-4'), 6.1 (1H, *d*, *J*=15 Hz, *H*-3'). (Found: C, 78.02; H, 11.01. C₁₆H₃₂O₂ requires C, 78.03; H, 11.03%).

4-(2'-Methyl-butadienyl)-5,9-dimethyl-8-decen-1-ol (IX): A mixture of VIII (4 g), PTS (500 mg), water (8 ml) and acetone (50 ml) was stirred for 24 hr at room temp. The usual work up followed by chromatographic purification furnished IX (2.39 g, 70%); ir: 2720, 1710, 1645, 1610, 970, 885; pmr (CCl₄): δ 1.0 [3H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH(CH₃)-],

1.15-1.45 (4H, *m*, *H*-3 and *H*-6), 1.6, 1.7 [3H, 3H, *s*, *s*, =C(CH₃)₂], 1.87 [3H, *s*, -CH=CH-C(CH₃)=CH₂], 1.9-2.4 (6H, *m*, *H*-2, *H*-4, *H*-5 and *H*-7), 4.85 (2H, *s*, *H*-1'), 5.1 (1H, *br*, *H*-8), 5.87 (1H, *dd*, *J*=7 and 14 Hz, *H*-4'), 6.1 (1H, *d*, *J*=15 Hz, *H*-3'), 9.3 (1H, *s*, *H*-1). (Found: C, 82.12; H, 11.18. C₁₇H₂₈O requires C, 82.20; H, 11.36%).

6-(2'-Methyl-butadienyl)-7,11-dimethyl-1,10-dodecadien-3-ol (X), Biflora-4,15-dien-10-one (XI) and Biflora-4,10(19),15-triene (I) were prepared by known procedure⁸. Identity of the synthetic compound was confirmed by comparing its spectral data with that recorded in literature^{8,9}.

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